

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Re-Viewing the Mass Communication Education Curriculum. Case for Language/Linguistics, Communication Synergy.

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Abstract: Curriculum review of any academic curriculum is one way of demonstrating the dynamism of such discipline. Mass Communication as a dynamic discipline is one such beneficiary of curriculum review. In line with Iwuchukwu's (2010) earlier submission that no graduate of any academic level or discipline worth's more than the curriculum that produces him/her, it was an observed inability of some practicing journalists, especially, those in the print. To handle ethical issues, which was traced to a lacuna in the curriculum that led to the introduction of the course, ethics. This paper seeks to unveil another obvious lapse among mass communication practitioners cutting across, print, broadcast and electronic media. It further highlights that such lapses as incompetence in language use, both at the phonetic, phonological semantic. Syntactic stylistic and even psycholinguistic to be a direct fall out of a perceived lacuna in the present mass communication education curriculum especially in Nigeria. We contend that a review of the present curriculum is glaringly imperative recommending not only the inclusion of more language/linguistic courses but also a stronger synergy between language/linguistics and mass communication. This is our opinion could be boosted with a course "Language and Communication not only though to all mass communication students at all levels, but it being recognized as another Sub-field of specialization by mass communication graduates who wish to further their stadium at the postgraduates levels as in the case in the University of Calabar.

Keywords Mass Communication, Education Curriculum, Language, Linguistics, Communication Synergy.

INTRODUCTION

An academic discipline is termed to be dynamic if its curriculum undergoes a periodic review. A graduate or professional of any academic discipline will normally function or perform within the ambits of the curriculum that he went through. Iwuchukwu (2010:118) captured this

fact earlier this way:

Every graduate in any academic discipline is always a product of the Curriculum that made him and nothing more. Just as the saying goes that the servant cannot be above his master, it takes extra-ordinary Circumstances and situations for one to be greater (know more) than the curriculum that he went through. A thoroughly bred scholar is usually a product of a thoroughly bred curriculum. It may not be unconnected with this fact that the Federal Government through the National Universities Commission has called for a general review of the curriculum of the most academic programmes in our universities. They realize albeit late that the existing curricular that produced graduates of the various disciplines in the 19th and 20th centuries cannot and is not meeting the needs of the graduates of the 21st century.

The Present Mass Communication Curriculum benefited from a review. When some practicing journalists, especially, those in the print had challenges in handling ethical issues, it was traced to a lacuna in the curriculum that existed. The curriculum was reviewed to accommodate the introduction of the teaching of the course ethics. This paper canvases for another review of the present Mass Communication Curriculum in Nigeria. This position is not just to acknowledge and accommodate the age-long relationship between language and Communication but to equip Mass Communication graduates of the 21st century to remedy observed lapses and incompetence in the language used by both print and Broadcast Media Practitioners.

LITERATURE REVIEW.

Several researchers have worked on the age-long relationship between Language/Linguistics and Communication. In this work, we are using the language and linguistic terms together in the sense that both overlap in our context. Language is the specie specific human possession according to Chomsky while linguistics is the scientific study of language. Both language and its scientific analysis have an intricate relationship with Communication. Allwood (1993:3) had captured this in his work on Language Communication and Social Activity where he said that without Communication, which is for the most part linguistic, most collective activities could not exist. He further states that,

Communication stands in as universal means-end relations to human collective activities. As soon as human beings need to be Coordinated in a joint activity, joint information is needed for the coordination. The information becomes joint by communication -which is mostly linguistic. However, whether verbal or not, there is always Communication as soon as we have coordinated activity and this communication is frequently verbally linguistic, even in cases where other types of communication are possible.

Allwood's analysis further showed that essential aspects of the organization of a social structure such as (a) distribution of power, (b) relations of affinity, (c) distribution of labour and (d) distribution of information, are initiated and sometimes constituted, upheld and charged through communication. His work further revealed that while communication is an essential aspect of both static and dynamic social structures, its multidimensional and contextual, is casually complex, acts of communication both with their surrounding non-communicative (non-linguistic) context and with their surrounding communicative (linguistic) context. His kind of concluding remark on the topic is if we wish to know how social activities influence communication we can regard the activity –its function/purpose, its roles, its tools, and its natural institutional and artificial environment as determining factors influencing both individual communication acts and interactive collective patterns of communication.

Wilson has been leading voice in the proposal for a language/linguistics (language Arts) and communication synergy campaign. Both Wilson (2016) and (2015) were devoted significantly to discussion and effort to demonstrating the complementary that should exist between Language/Linguistics and Communication. Wilson (2016) argued on the relevance and strategic role of language arts in the development of the communication studies curriculum. He was very categorical in stating that” *Language is the vehicle for communication and whatever skills are needed for the effective production of any language are the skills needed for Communication*” (Wilson 2016:3). He emphasized the role of the Language Arts in the delivery of a credible training curriculum for Communication Students in Nigeria. According to him, “*it is a known fact that for anyone to use and practice the skills and arts of communication, they should have a full grasp of language and communication, origins and transmutations.* He recommended some linguistic/language arts courses which will make any communication study curriculum solid and credible, Furthermore, in both Wilson (2015) and (2016), He succinctly articulated the need to lead mass communication students into a knowledge of the psycholinguistic underpinnings as well as the environment and situations in which such messages are audited, the arts and skills of producing effective messages and the conditions which make message reception effective even when feedback may be variable.

Ndimele and Solo (2016) are not left out in the debate. They harped on the need to employ linguistics resources to aid in the training of persons in other progressions/disciplines especially, Journalism and some Professions of Persuasion. They went ahead to x-ray the relevance of language/linguistics I the mass communication profession Ndimele and Solo (2016:22-) spelled out the details of language/linguistics in news writing. Here, they show that linguistic knowledge is imperative to enhance their reportorial and communication ability, to be able to explore stylistic contrasts in the portrayed of currents, to learn how to use punctuation marks and tenses accurately, etc. In proofreading, He shows that the proofreader/editor requires excellent exposure to linguistics resources among others, develop critical eyes and evaluative mind to know which aspect of the news items or a manuscript must be deleted, retained or rephrased before it is published or goes on-air as well as to be at home with spellings of words in hi working language. In creating Headlines, they believe, requires special skill in journalism which requires human language and the impact of words. In Broadcasting according to them, the newscaster/presenter of programmes in the broadcast media should among others

- (a) Receive training in pronunciation and vocal efficiency.
- (b) Be familiar with the intonations and stress patterns that obtain in his working language.
- (c) Be familiar with a working range of distinctive human speech sounds as well as to know how to produce them.
- (d) To be familiar with the orthographies of languages, especially those within his working area.
- (e) To undergo intensive oral drills, if he has ‘Heavy’ native language interference that can blur Comprehension on the part of his listeners; the oral drills can be centered around the areas where there are misleading similarities between sounds in his native language and those of his working language. Since the pronunciation of cultural words/names poses a problem to the broadcasters, they need to write such names with phonetics transcription. Only reporters who are trained in phonetics can transcribe words correctly. Ndimele and Solo (2016:24) further showed the relevance of language/linguistics in other professions of persuasion including, advertising, public relations, propaganda, and marketing. Their submissions on this are presented as follows;

Our position is that in all these professions of persuasion, humans are often manipulated not necessarily by our actions, but largely by how the resources of language are harnessed to achieve the desired purpose. We argue that Persuasion

Communicators do need a course that teaches how linguistic resources can be explored to improve their imaginative and creative ability in manipulating, Persuading or massaging the emotions of their target population.

Odegbenle, (2013) Lamented on the challenges of the language of communication in the Nigerian Media. Odegbenle (2013:3) declared that "Communicating in the appropriate language is becoming a source of worry to language experts especially, on media contents. This concern is hinged on the belief that the media is the conscience of the society and that people have a greater inclination to believe their messages. The fear is the misuse of language of communication in the mass media in Nigeria to promote violence and vulgarity "He maintained that communication experts have established that in some cases, inappropriate choice of words and bad contextual applications of the language rob the audience of the proper understanding of the message and lead to public rage. Harub *et al* (2003:1) in their inquiry about the origin of language and communication, after examining the anatomical and physiological requirements averred that *the evidence conclusively implies that humans were created with the unique ability to employ speech for communication*".

Looking at such an intricate relationship between language/linguistics and mass communication, from origin to date, it is still bewildering to see that this has not reflected in most mass communication curriculum content from undergraduate to postgraduate levels. This work is not only to strengthen the position of the scholars pointed above to show practically the consequences of the neglect of the language and linguistic input but also to suggest more pertinent linguistic courses needed to be added to every communication studies curriculum (those not in Wilson's 2016 presentation) as well the need to recognise Language and Communication Research as a sub-field of specialization at the graduate level of Mass Communication Programmes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted in this work is qualitative research, specifically, content analysis. The mass communication curriculum of the Cross River State University of Technology, served as the reference material while that of the Universities of Calabar and Port-Harcourt were only content examined, hence they provide the kind of synergy which we are canvassing for. A Nigerian newspaper (The PUNCH) and the NATION were also content analysed to practically demonstrate what is being theoretically postulated. As earlier discussed, the new courses recommended by Wilson (2016) were equally examined so that they need not be repeated in our new recommendations. A graduate course designed and thought in the University of Calabar was also examined and presented as part of the data. Secondary source materials were equally helpful. These data will be presented and discussed in subsequent sub-sections with a summary of findings. Present Mass Communication Curriculum of Cross River University of Technology excluding General Studies Courses.

TABLE 1:
Details of the Academic Programme of the Department
Year One.
First Semester Courses.

Code	Course	Credit Units
MAC 1101	Introduction to Mass Communication	2
MAC 1102	History of Nigerian Mass Media	2
MAC1103	Introduction to Photography	2
MAC 1104	Introduction to French 1	2

MAC 1105	Nigerian Legal System	2
Elective:	Anyone of following (MAC 1106 - MAC 110)	Elective
MAC 1106	Introduction to Political Science	2
MAC 1107	Introduction to Sociology	2
MAC 110	Introduction to Psychology	2
STAT 1101	Introduction to Statistics	2

Second Semester Courses:

Code	Courses	Credits Hours
MAC 1201	Introduction to Broadcasting	2
MAC 1202	African Communication System	2
MAC 1203	Introduction to Desktop Publishing	2
MAC 1204	Principle of Public Speaking	2
MAC 1205	Basic English for Media Writers	2
MAC 1206	Introduction to French 2	2

YEAR TWO:

First Semester Courses

Code	Courses	Credits Units
MAC 2101	News Writing and Reporting	2
MAC 2102	Mass Media and Society	2
MAC 2103	Writing for the Mass Media	2
MAC 2104	Intermediate French 1	2
MAC 2105	Principle of Advertising	2
MAC 2106	Online Journalism	2
MAC 2107	Broadcasting Studio Production Techniques	2

Second Semester Courses

Code	Courses	Credit Units
MAV 2201	Internet and its Application	2
MAC 2202	Reviewing and Criticism	2
MAC 2203	Specialized Reporting for Multi-Media	2
MAC 2204	Intermediate French 2	2
MAC 2205	Principles of Public Relations	2
MAC 2206	Feature/Writing for Multi-Media	2
MAC 2207	Broadcasting Presentation	2
MAC 220	Video Field Production Techniques	2

YEAR THREE:

First Semester

Code	Courses	Credit Units
MAC 3101	Principle of Visual Communication	2
MAC 3102	International Communication	2
MAC 3103	Broadcasting Programming & Production	2
MAC 3104	Environmental Reporting	2
MAC 3105	Newspaper Production Laboratory	2
MAC 3106	Advance Media Writing	2
MAC 3107	Elements of Field Production	2

Elective: (Anyone of the following –MAC 310 -3111)

MAC 310	Magazine Article Writing	2
MAC 310	Principles & Practice of Book Publishing	2
MAC 3110	Advancing Creative Strategies	2
MAC 3111	Corporate Communication Techniques	2

Second Semester:

Code	Courses	Credit Units
MAC 3201	Science and Technology Reporting	2
MAC 3202	Aesthetics of Film and Video	2
MAC 3203	Mass Communication Research	2
MAC3204	Principle and Practice of Photojournalism	2
MAC 3205	Computer Graphic Application	2
MAC 3206	Broadcast News, Editing & Production	2
MAC 3207	Internship	2
MAC 320	Advance Magazine Article Writing	2
MAC 320	International Public Relations	2
MAC 3210	Management PR & Ad Agency	2
MAC 3211	Advance Book Publishing Techniques	2

YEAR FOUR,

First Semester:

Code	Courses	Credit Units
MAC 4101	Communication Law, Ethnic Responsibility	2
MAC 4102	Editorial Writing	2
MAC 4103	Data Analysis in Communication Research	2
MAC 4104	Seminar	2
MAC 4105	Media Management	2
MAC 4106	Broadcasting Commentary Production	2
MAC 4107	Mass Communication Theory	2

Elective:	Anyone of the following (MAC4108 -4110)	Electives
MAC 4108	Public Relations and Campaigns	2
MAC 4109	Contemporary Magazine Publishing	2
MAC 4110	Book Publishing in the Digital Age	2

Second Semester:

Code	Courses	Credit Units
MAC 4201	Investigative & Interpretative	2
MAC4202	Drama & Documentary Production	2
MAC 4203	Website Management	2
MAC 4204	Educational Broadcasting	2
MAC4205	Research Project	6

1.4 Data Presentation, Discussion and Summary of Findings

Table 2: Linguistics and Communication Studies Programme: University of Calabar

YEAR ONE--- SEMESTER ONE

Credit

Course Code	Course Title	Hours	Status
LCS 101	Introduction to Linguistics & Communication 1	3	Compulsory
LCS 111	Introduction to Phonetics 1	3	Compulsory
LCS 151	Human Communication	3	Compulsory
FRT 181	Introduction to French Language 1	3	Compulsory
LCS 131	Languages of the World	2	Optional
LCS 121	Efik/Ibibio/Bekwara/Ejagham Languages	2	Optional
LCS 141	English Grammar 1	2	Optional
Total Credit Hours		18	

YEAR ONE—SEMESTER TWO

Course Code	Course Title	Credit Hours	Status
LCS 102	Introduction to Linguistics & Communication	3	Compulsory
LCS 111	Introduction to Phonetics 11	3	Compulsory
LCS 162	Language use in the Media	3	Compulsory
LCS 152	Development in Communication Technology	3	Compulsory
FRT 182	Introduction to French Language	3	Compulsory
LCS 132	History of Linguistics	2	Optional
LCS 122	Efik/Ibibio/Bekwara/Ejagham Culture	2	Optional
LCS 142	English Grammar 11	2	Optional

N/B: Students should offer optional courses from each semester

YEAR TWO—(DIRECT ENTRY) SEMESTER ONE

Course Code	Course Title	Credit Hours	Status
LCS 101	Introduction to Linguistics & Communication. 1	3	Compulsory
LCS 201	Phonology	3	Compulsory
LCS 221	Introduction to Morphology	3	Compulsory
LCS 231	Writing, Systems/Orthographic Design	3	Compulsory
LCS 251	Language and Broadcasting	3	Compulsory
FRT 181	Introduction to French Lang.	3	Compulsory

YEAR TWO—SEMESTER TWO

Credit				
Course Code	Course Title	Hours	Status	
LCS 102	Introduction to Linguistic & Communication. 1	3	Compulsory	
LCS 202	Generative Phonology	3	Compulsory	
LCS 222	Morphologies of African Languages	3	Compulsory	
LCS 242	Language and Public Relation	3	Compulsory	
LCS 272	Principles of Advertising	3	Compulsory	
FRT 182	Introduction to French Language 11	3	Compulsory	

YEAR THREE—SEMESTER ONE

		Credit		
Course Code	Course Title	Hours	Status	
LCS 301	Introduction to Syntax	3	Compulsory	
LCS 321	Structure of a Language 1	3	Compulsory	
LCS 331	Applied Linguistics	3	Compulsory	
LCS 351	Proof Reading Technique	3	Compulsory	
ELECTIVE	Any 3 rd year 1 st Semester Course from Faculty of Education or Department Of Sociology.	3	Elective	
LCS 311	Dialectology	2	Optional	
LCS 381	English in the Nigerian Setting	2	Optional	
LCS 391	Organizational Communication	2	Optional	
LCS 341	Computation/Practical Linguistics	2	Optional	
LCS 361	Health Communication	2	Optional	

YEAR THREE—SEMESTER TWO

Credit		Status		
Course Code	Course Title	Hours	Status	
LCS 302	Generative Syntax	3	Compulsory	
LCS 322	Structure of a Language 11	2	Optional	
LCS 332	Linguistics and Communication	2	Compulsory	
LCS 342	Research Method Applied	2	Compulsory	
LCS 372	Communication Sociolinguistics	2	Compulsory	
LCS 382	Consultancy in Communication	2	Compulsory	
ELECTIVE	Any 3 rd year 2 nd Semester Course form the Faculty of Education or Department	3	Elective	

		of sociology.		
LCS	312	Contrastive/Error Analysis	2	Optional
LCS	362	Drama and Poetry in Efik/ Bekwara/Ejagham		
LCS	375	Introduction to African Linguistics	2	Optional
LCS	352	Communication and Culture	2	Optional
LCS	302	Entrepreneurship	2	Compulsory
LCS	392	Trade Skill Internship	3	Compulsory

N/B: Students should offer the optional course from each semester

N/B: Students offer one optional course from each semester

YEAR FOUR—FIRST SEMESTER

Course Code	Course Title	Credit Hours	Status
LCS 4001	Topics in Phonology	3	
	Compulsory		
LCS 4011	Semantics and	3	
	Compulsory		
LCS 4021	Translation Lexicology &	3	
	Compulsory		
LCS 4031	Lexicography Indigenous	3	
	Compulsory		
LCS 4075	Communication Systems & Semiotics Theories of	3	
	Compulsory		
LCS 4111	Communication Linguistics & Literature	2	
	Optional		
LCS 4121	Speech Pathology	2	
	Optional		
LCS 4131	Historical/Comparative Linguistics	2	
	Optional		
LCS 4041	Rhetorical Theory & Practice	2	
	Optional		

YEAR FOUR—SEMESTER TWO

Course Code	Course Title	Hour	Credit	Status
LCS 4002	Topics in Syntax	3		Compulsory
LCS 4012	Psycholinguistics	3		Compulsory
LCS 4032	Language of Features & Commentary	3		Compulsory
LCS 4090	General Paper	3		Compulsory

LCS	4092	Research Project (Long Essay)	6	Compulsory
LCS	4112	Politician Communication	2	Optional
LCS	4122	Problem of a Multilingual Nation	2	Optional
LCS	4132	Comparative Cross River Languages	2	Optional
LCS	4042	Languages and Argument	2	Optional

Table 3:

Evidence of deficiencies from practitioners and professionals:

The Nation (Monday, October 30th, 2017).

On page 2: ‘Positioning Nigeria for a prosperous future’, the word ‘a similar’ was written as one word ‘a similar’.

On page 7: ‘Southeast leaders seek repairs of federal roads, Enugu airport. There is an error in the use of the plural marker ‘s’ in others(Other dignitaries included.....)

On page 7- ‘Grammatical error ‘Okonkwo rallies support for Obiano’ the noun ‘weight’ is used as a verb in this sentence ‘They have been fairly weighted and properly scale....’

On-Page 8- Grammatical error in this sentence ‘Udi LGA has 20 wards’. There is no plural marker in the ward.

There is also spelling error- ‘..... sneak in through the back door at the midnight.....’

There is mechanical accuracy error in this sentence ‘we therefore respectfully pray.....’the use of comma after ‘we’ was omitted.

Table 4:

Language and use Communication Courses taught at the MA/Ph.D level at the University of Calabar; Code LCS 6041.

Course Description:

Language and Communication (L&C), an interdisciplinary course within the Faculty of Arts, centres on the study and use of language in society in a multilingual, globalized world, with a particular focus on Language global import, such as English, as well as those with local significance, in how they are appropriated and positioned in multilingual, cosmopolitan contexts of Nigeria. The course provides the theoretical foundations and applied contexts for understanding and addressing linguistics and social questions of Language and Communication. It equips students with the intellectual and practical tools to critically examine, intelligently reflect on, and competently participate in communicative situations, in real-world contents, such as in the workplace, lecture delivery as well as in more informal sites of multilingual communication. The L&C course take s particular pride in engaging in experiment learning, from projects involving fieldwork in Nigeria to a practical case studies of language and communication interrelationship. In addressing the need in society for linguistically versatile and cultural sensitive learners in the 21st-century knowledge economy of Nigeria's world, city and beyond, the course aims at honing transferable skills for a wide range of careers, including education, material development, editing

and publishing, public administration, public relations, marketing, the media, event organization, tourism, cultural affairs, and global creative industries.

Expectations:

Students who declare a major or minor in Language Communication will:

- identify and critique relevant issues in the study of Language and Communication, and apply theoretical and methodological knowledge to real-world social and linguistics data;
- critically evaluate established knowledge and creatively apply it to novel, contemporary contexts of communication, in this multilingual, globalized world, in particular in the settings of Nigeria;
- critically reflect upon the strengths and weakness of her own others' viewpoints and communicative practices, and challenges taken-for-granted assumption about language and communication;
- identify, appreciate and critically examine the role of diversity in languages and communicative strategies across cultures and time, and how this shapes one's linguistic identity and comes to bear upon communicative situations, drawing on cross-cultural perspective in the study of language and communication;
- use the necessary intellectual, communicative and practical skills to participate in intellectual discussions of linguistic and social issues and collaborate productively in projects, in and for both institutional and real-world contexts;
- demonstrate an understanding of the complexities of contemporary social and political issues of language and communication in the context of globalization, such as the appropriation and positioning of languages of global significance, in particular, English, and the fine balance struck with other local languages. With a view to sustainability in multilingual, cosmopolitan contexts of Nigeria-which allows for intelligent, significant and responsible contribution =s to society.

(1) Introduction:

a (i) Definitions

(ii) Components of languages

b (i) what is communication?

(ii) Principles of communication

(iii) Types of communication

(iv) Conversational maxims

(v) Violating the conversational maxims

(2) Origin of language and communication

(3) a. Relationship between language and communication,

b. Difference between language and communication

(4) Communication and Language Development;

-Physical and brain development

-Babbling as a gateway to advance communication

-Language use and Television Viewing

-Communicating peace through mother to child language talks

(5) Practical and recent case studies in language communication research in Nigeria

(6) Environmental print communication awareness in language development

(7)Theorizing communication

(8)Introduction to global creative industries

(9)Intercultural communication

(10) Adaptation from text to screen

(11) Exploring language use in mass communication

- a. Broadcasting
- b. Print
- c. ICT
- d. Social Media

(11) Language, Linguistics and Communication Programme Domiciliation Controversy.

DISCUSSION

The disparity in language/Linguistics content in the two programmes of the two institutions is very glaring. The institution with Mass Communication code name lacks serious Linguistics/Language courses unlike the institution with the code: Linguistics and Communication on Studies. As stated earlier, institutions with Mass Communication Code name tend to share the same Curriculum Content through the NUC B MAS as observed by Wilson (2016) while those with linguistics and Communication or Language/arts tend to share similar curricular content. Wilson (2016) observed that *"NUC has been a common curriculum for the study of all the variants of Communication studies in our Universities ... They all embrace the Minimum Academic Standards (MAS) document, while also focusing on some special areas of their own"*. We share his candid opinion that NUC does not worry about the content of the programmes as much as they worry about the code name. That is why they are gross erroneously insisting on Linguistics and Communication Studies or Communication and Language Arts Programme must revert to Mass Communication. This recommendation tends to be born out of imperialist influence of exoglossic Scholars rather than empirical and historical facts as articulated by some scholars in this work: knowledge and competence in language use remains significantly relevant in the competence and performance of virtually all mass communication sub-field such as broadcasting, print, journalism, ICT and even social media.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

A comparison of the two curricula shows that the institutions with the Mass Communication Code name will produce graduates without any idea or introduction to Language/Linguistics, Phonetics, Morphology, Discourse Analysis, and Pragmatics. This is the Synergy that will equip Communication graduate with appropriate Language and Language and Linguistics resources is an invaluable assets that will bring about competence and effectiveness among Mass Communication Practitioners and Educators in Nigeria in the 21st Century. This could even still be a trending or novel idea if exported globally. Graduates of such curriculum are more equipped and balanced than those otherwise. Language and linguistics studies synergy with mass communication programmes remain among the best innovative methodologies to not only strengthen the capacity of the professionals but also deepening inter-disciplinary research produced.

CONCLUSION

This work is an added voice to the several expert voices calling for the review of the present Mass Communication Curriculum and re-designation of the code name of such programmes in the light of the present realities. From theoretical postulations to a kind of field work/report, there seen to be overwhelming endorsement of the incorporation of more languages/linguistic courses as suggested above and by other experts into the Mass Communication Curriculum. If this cannot be achieved except with the re-designation of the code name from Mass Communication to Communication Studies., Linguistics and Communication, or Communication Arts, let the designation to be done expeditiously. Rather than dissipate energy on the code name, focus should be on the content. The curriculum content should align with the

age-long historical, physiological, anatomical and complimentary relationships shared by Language/Linguistics and Communications. Towards achieving the goal, Postgraduate Programmes should be designed and mounted in Language and Communication for more research into this sub-field and ultimately, the production of more experts equipped to excel in any field of Communication Practice of education.

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